

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

DELIVERABLE 3.1

Demonstrator of an integrated drone-based survey system

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Executive Summary

Brief Overview

This report, Deliverable 3.1 (D3.1) of the AGEMERA project, focuses on the integrated drone-based survey system developed by Radai Oy. The report summarises the research and development efforts undertaken to advance the field of drone-based geophysical surveying and briefly describes the next steps.

Objectives and Scope

The primary objective of D3.1 is to demonstrate the present status of the development work made on Radai's integrated drone-based survey system in the AGEMERA project. The report focuses on the following four topics:

- Drone-platform,
- Radiometric survey system,
- Magnetic survey system, and
- Electromagnetic survey system.

Key Findings

1. **Selection of suitable drone-platform:** The report presents the specifications of the VTOL (Vertical Take-Off and Landing) drone (called in this report as 'Coot') selected as the drone platform for the integrated survey system. Due to the mass/weight of the radiometric system, the EM system cannot be utilised at the same time, but the same drone can be utilised in both tasks.
2. **Radiometric system:** The outcome from the tests made with the radiometric system are two-fold. On one hand the radiometric system was successfully installed on a VTOL drone and the flight tests were successfully made, but on the other hand, the radiometric system itself was not working as well as expected.
3. **Magnetic system:** Radai's existing magnetic survey system was successfully installed on a Coot drone, and the data obtained from the tests was found to be of good quality. Compared to the Puffin VTOL drones that Radai has previously used for magnetic surveys, the bigger size of the Coot drone provides an almost 100% increase in efficiency due to the longer flight endurance (2 h vs 1 h).
4. **Electromagnetic system:** The development of a fully airborne EM system has succeeded only partially. The field tests made in August 2024 show that the semi-airborne version of the Louhi EM system is fully operational except for the lack of phase calibration (transmitter-receiver time synchronisation). Moreover, measurements made with the small transmitter loop on the ground level were

successful as well as the flight tests with inactive transmitter loop. Occasionally, however, the transmitter's EM field distorts the autopilot of the Coot drone, thus, preventing safe flight operations. The first field tests with the single-drone Louhi EM system are expected after successful integration tests in 2025.

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List of Acronyms

D4	Fourth difference
DC	Direct current
DEM	Digital elevation model
DSP	Digital signal processing
CRS	Coordinate reference system
ELM	Equivalent layer modelling
EM	Electromagnetic
FG	Fluxgate
GNSS	Global satellite navigation system
GPS	Global positioning system
HP	High pass (filtering)
IMU	Inertial measurement unit
L	Loop separation (Tx-Rx)
Lion	Lithium-ion (battery)
LiPo	Lithium-polymer (battery)
LP	Low pass (filtering)
MSS	Magnetic survey system
PC	Personal computer
QA/QC	Quality assurance / quality control
RAD	Radai Ltd
RMP	Radai multi-purpose (datalogger)
RTP	Reduced to pole
RSS	Radiometric survey system
Rx	Receiver (unit)
SCI	Photon scintillation counter
SD	Secure digital (card)
TMI	Total magnetic intensity
Tx	Transmitter (unit)
UAV	Unoccupied aerial vehicle
USB	Universal serial bus
VTOL	Vertical take-off and landing
WGS84	World geodetic system 1984

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

1.1.1 AGEMERA Project

The AGEMERA project focuses on advancing mineral exploration methods in the European Union (EU) and Zambia to meet the demands of a low-carbon and digital economy. Utilising a combination of conventional and state-of-the-art geological and geophysical surveys, the project aims to map Critical Raw Material (CRM) resources across approximately 4,700 km² in seven countries. It will employ three innovative, non-invasive survey techniques — passive seismic methods, multi-sensing drone system, and muon-based multidetector density detection system (utilising a novel astroparticle physics technique called muon imaging or muography) — to enhance the accuracy of existing genetic mineral system models. Concurrently, the project will engage with stakeholders to introduce United Nations Framework Classification (UNFC) guidelines for mineral resources and will undertake extensive public outreach, targeting an audience of 5,000,000 citizens by 2030. Additionally, AGEMERA will develop an open-access SoftGIS database to capture social, cultural, environmental, and economic concerns related to mining, thereby facilitating the creation of socio-economic potential maps to be used alongside geological potential maps.

1.1.2 Present Report's Place in the AGEMERA Project

The present report is an output of WP3 of the AGEMERA project. AGEMERA is subdivided into seven (7) Work Packages (WPs): WP1 European CRM Potential, WP2 Impact of CRM on Green & Digital Transition, WP3 Geophysical Data Acquisition, WP4 Data Processing, Fusion & Sharing, WP5 Dissemination, Communication & Collaboration, WP6 Exploitation and WP7 Management. WP4 has solid links to the first three WPs.

WP3 is subdivided into four (4) tasks: **T3.1 Drone-based magnetic, radiometric, and electromagnetic surveys**, T3.2 Integrated muon-based density surveys, T3.3 Validation and calibration of passive seismic for mineral exploration, and T3.4. Field data collection & storage. The present report is a deliverable of T3.1. This task is led and run almost entirely by RAD.

1.1.3 Study Areas

The AGEMERA project concentrates its field tests in several geological areas in Europe and in Zambia. Radai's drone-based technology is applied in Finland, Bosnia-Herzegovina, and Bulgaria. The magnetic surveys in Zambia are made by Radai's local affiliate, Zanifi Ltd.

1.2 Objectives of the Report

The primary objective of this report, which serves as Deliverable 3.1 (D3.1) of AGEMERA, is to elucidate the methodologies and outcomes of Task 3.1, titled “integrated drone-based survey system.” Note that some tasks of T3.1 are still ongoing. For example, field tests in Bosnia-Herzegovina and Bulgaria ended 22.9.20224.

The objectives of T3.1 are related to following topics:

- Drone-platform,
- Radiometric survey system,
- Magnetic survey system, and
- Electromagnetic survey system.

This report aims to offer a comprehensive view on the status of Task 3.1 in Fall 2024.

1.3 Structure of the Report

This report is organised into a series of interconnected chapters and subsections, each designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the workflow process for combining various datasets acquired in the AGEMERA project. The structure is as follows:

- **Chapter 1: Introduction:** This chapter describes the
- **Chapter 2: Drone platform:** This chapter describes the specifications of the VTOL drone chosen as the platform on which the various measurement devices are installed.
- **Chapter 3. Radiometric survey system:** This chapter provides information about the development work made on the radiometric survey system (RSS).
- **Chapter 4. Magnetic survey system:** This chapter describes Radai’s magnetic survey system (MSS) installed on the Coot drone.
- **Chapter 5. Electromagnetic survey system:** This chapter describes the development work made on Radai’s Louhi EM system.
- **Chapter 6 – Conclusions and road ahead:** This chapter summarises the development work in task T3.1 so far and discusses the future work.

2. Coot VTOL drone platform

2.1 Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) drone

Radai's integrated drone-based survey system will be installed onto VTOL (Vertical Take-Off and Landing) type of drone called Coot illustrated in Figure 1. Coot VTOL drone is based on the Fighter drone-kit by Makeflyeasy company. Technical parameters of the Coot VTOL drone are given in Table 1.

Figure 1. The Coot VTOL drone is based on Fighter VTOL drone by Makeflyeasy. (<http://en.makeflyeasy.com>).

Table 1. Technical specifications of the Coot VTOL drone.

Parameter	Value
Mass	12 kg with 2 x 6S LiPo batteries
Max take-off weight	14.5 kg
Wingspan	2.43 m
Electric engines	4 x 1000W + 2000W
Flight speed	20 m/s
Endurance	2 h (w/o payload) 1 h (with EM or radiometric system)
Max. range	140 km (w/o payload) 70 km (with EM or radiometric system)

2.2 Modifications made on Coot VTOL drone

Since Fighter by Makeflyeasy it is a drone-kit, it requires that all its components are installed, glued, and/or screwed one by one and the wirings for the individual electrical components, such as the motors, autopilot, servos, and flight control modules, electric speed controls, airspeed sensors, etc.

To be able to utilise the radiometric system on the Coot VTOL drone, the bottom of the fuselage needs to be opened to accommodate the gamma ray detector. Except for safe attachment of the detector, no major modifications are needed in the instalment of the radiometric system. The radiometer data, total intensity as the number of counts or counts per second (cps) in the gamma ray detector, are recorded with Radai's multipurpose (RMP) datalogger.

To enable the magnetic system on the Coot VTOL drone; 1) all ferromagnetic (iron-bearing) elements (screws, bolts, nuts, and washers) are removed from the tail end of the drone, 2) servos are placed inside the fuselage and push bars are used to operate the tail elevators and rudder, 3) an extended tail pipe with an inner diameter of one inch is rigidly attached behind the tail. The fluxgate magnetometer sensor will be installed in the tail boom to increase the distance, and thus, to reduce the magnetic noise from the main engine in the front of the Coot drone.

To facilitate electromagnetic measurements, two modifications are made on the Coot VTOL drone. Firstly, a hook lock connected to a remotely operated servo is attached at the bottom of the drone. The lock can be opened, and the tow line can be detached from the drone before landing by a switch on the handheld radio transmitter of the pilot. Secondly, the small transmitter loop used in the fully airborne version of Louhi EM system is rigidly attached around the Coot VTOL. The loop passes through the fuselage in the front but otherwise it is located below the wings. The purpose of this installation is to keep drone's centre of gravity in the optimal place. If needed, the small loop transmitter can be detached and attached again in few minutes.

In all three systems, separate GNSS antenna providing positioning and timing data to the RMP datalogger and/or EM transmitter device is installed on the backside of the drone (cf. Figure 6). This secondary antenna is positioned closer to the tail to prevent interference with the primary GNSS antenna used by the autopilot. In a similar manner, a passthrough is made on drone's roof hatch for a 3G/4G antenna.

3. Radiometric survey system

3.1 Radai's RSS concept

Gamma-ray spectroscopy is the quantitative study of the energy spectra of gamma-ray sources, such as in the nuclear industry, geochemical investigation, and astrophysics. When these emissions are detected and analyzed with a spectroscopy system, a gamma-ray energy spectrum can be produced to distinguish the source of the gamma rays.

Four most important natural gamma radiation sources are as follows

1. **Potassium-40 (^{40}K):** A common element found in rocks and soil, emitting gamma radiation as it decays. Potassium emits gamma radiation at 1.46 MeV.
2. **Uranium-238 (^{238}U):** Naturally occurring in the Earth's crust, its decay series produces gamma radiation. Produces gamma rays, notably 1.76 MeV from bismuth-214 (^{214}Bi).
3. **Thorium-232 (^{232}Th):** Found in soil and rocks, its decay series emits gamma rays from thallium-208 (^{208}Tl) at 2.62 MeV.
4. **Radon (^{222}Rn):** A radioactive gas from uranium decay. Decay products like lead-214 (^{214}Pb) and bismuth-214 (^{214}Bi) emit gamma rays at 0.61 MeV, 1.12 MeV, and 1.76 MeV.

Radai's partner company, Georadis (www.georadis.com), specialises in the development and construction of gamma-ray spectrometers and total radiometric counters, leveraging over 30 years of expertise in radiometric survey systems.

Unfortunately, there are currently no suitable radiometric survey solutions on the market for mineral exploration that offer both a lightweight payload and an affordable price. As a result, Radai and Georadis developed the radiometric survey system (RSS) from scratch for this project. Since the RSS will be used in a drone, the weight of the measuring device is a critical factor. A key innovation has been the use of a detector material that is significantly lighter than those found in conventional RSS detectors.

Figure 2 presents an early version of the system featuring two photon scintillation counters (SCI) and an analyzer attached to one of the SCIs. We have successfully tested several dataloggers (two prototypes of these are shown in Fig. 2) to ensure that data collection proceeds without issues. Table 2 lists the main parameters and functions of Radai/Georadis RSS system. Radai's RSS system measures the total radiometric counts.

Figure 2. Early prototype of the radiometric detector on a laboratory desk.

Table 2. Properties of the radiometric survey system.

Parameter	Function
PWR	Power Supply with output voltage 500V to scintillator
SCI	Scintillation photon counter to transform the energy of photon to corresponding electrical signal.
ANZ	Analyzer and calibrator for measured electrical signal
LOG	Datalogger collects counts from each 4 channel

Figure 3. The radiometric detector attached at the bottom the Razorbill VTOL drone. Pilots Emma Tuunala and Timo Åman are just outside Radai's office.

The weight of the measurement system must be optimised to match the payload capacity of the chosen UAV. For this project, a vertical take-off and landing (VTOL) drone was selected to transport the measurement device. After intensive testing we selected Razorbill VTOL (See Figure 3), capable of carrying several kilograms. Table 3 lists some key details of Razorbill UAV.

Table 3. Technical specifications of the Razorbill VTOL drone.

Parameter	Value
Mass	12.5 kg with 2 x 6S LiPo batteries
Max take-off weight	15 kg
Wingspan	2.5 m
Electric engines	4 x 1000W + 2000W
Flight speed	26.5 m/s
Endurance	2 h (w/o payload) 0.5 h (with radiometric system)
Max. range	70 km (w/o payload)

3.2 Radiometric data example

In June 2024, Radai Oy made a radiometric survey over the Lintumaansuo test site located some 20 km north of Oulu. Total radiometric intensity from potassium, uranium, thorium and radon were measured. Figure 4 shows the topographic map of the survey area and two flight paths of the survey flights. The whole survey is about 40 line-km long. The line separation is 50 m, and line azimuth is 135 degrees from map east. The flight altitude was set to 30 m from the ground level (DEM).

Figure 4. Flight lines from a radiometric survey made at the Lintumaansuo test site. Topographic map and digital elevation model (DEM) by National Land Survey of Finland.

Figure 5 presents the measured total count at the Lintumaansuo test area. The survey was repeated twice to confirm the distinct and consistent patterns associated with radioactive sources beneath the flight paths. To gather sufficient data, the flight speed was maintained at approximately 3-5 m/s, resulting in nearly 2 hours per survey flight. In contrast, magnetic field measurements permit a flight speed that is ten times higher. Although it is feasible to collect both magnetic field and EM data in a single flight, the low altitude required for radiometric measurements limits the efficiency of such combined surveys.

Figure 5. Measured total radiometric intensity at the Lintumaansuo test site.

To facilitate agile processing and utilisation of the survey's raw data in the field, we have enhanced existing *RadaiPros/RadaiView* software (see Chapter 4.1) so that they can read and process the raw RSS data in addition to magnetic data. The final processing of RSS data into GeoTIFF grids is made using third-party software (e.g., Golden Software Surfer or QGIS). However, while this acceleration in the data processing chain is beneficial, it does not significantly mitigate the slower measurement speed required for the RSS.

Another issue is that the device remains too heavy, and currently, RSS may interfere with magnetic field measurements, although this has not been confirmed. Overall, we estimate the TR level of the radiometric device to be between 3 and 4.

4. Magnetic survey system

4.1 Radai's MSS concept

Radai's magnetic survey system is based on the use of a digital 3-component fluxgate (FG) magnetometer and Radai's multipurpose RMP datalogger. In addition to the three orthogonal components of the magnetic field, the RMP datalogger records temperature and barometric pressure, which is used to determine barometric flight altitude. The GNSS (GPS, Glonass, Galileo, and Beidou) time (UT) and position (latitude, longitude, and altitude) are also recorded. An inertial measurement unit (IMU) provides the orientation (roll, pitch, and yaw angles) of the drone. Special calibration measurement is made to determine the rotation angles that align the IMU and the FG sensors with each other. During flight, the horizontal accuracy of the GNSS positioning is below ± 0.5 m and vertical accuracy is less than ± 1 meter. Technical details of the system are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Technical parameters of the magnetic survey system.

Parameter (fluxgate)	Value
Noise level	± 0.5 nT
Dynamic range	± 100 μ T
Sampling frequency	135-140 Hz
Parameter (IMU)	Value
Dynamic accuracy	0.03 (roll & pitch)
	0.2 (yaw/heading)
Sampling frequency	up to 800 Hz (IMU)
	up to 400 Hz (GNSS)

As always in Radai's drone surveys, after take-off, the flight is controlled by an autopilot that guides the drone through a set of predefined waypoints. The flight path follows terrain topography defined by the digital elevation model (DEM) of the survey area. The flight performance and safety are monitored in real time by PC software via a wireless mobile 3G/4G link. After survey flight and drone landing the data are first read via WLAN connection onto a local PC laptop and then uploaded onto a cloud server (Google Drive). The data pre-processing and quality assessment (QA) and quality control (QC) are made remotely (normally in Oulu) by Radai's QA/QC personnel.

Magnetic base station near the mobile telemetry/control station measures the temporal variation of the magnetic field. In the post-processing of the data, the magnetic data of the moving drone platform are corrected for the temporal changes observed at the base station. Normally, a GEM Systems GSM-19T proton precession magnetometer with a 1 or 3 s sampling rate is used to record the base data.

Figure 6 shows the Coot VTOL drone used in the Lintumaansuo EM survey in summer 2024, where also the magnetic field was measured. The fluxgate magnetometer is located inside the tail boom about 1.4 m away from the main engine in the front. In Figure 6, the two small round cylinders on the drone roof are GNSS antennae and the longer slanted stick between them is the 3G/4G mobile network antenna.

Figure 6. Radai's magnetic survey system installed on a Coot VTOL drone. The fluxgate magnetometer is inside the extended tail boom of the drone.

4.2 Magnetic data processing

The magnetic data are processed using *RadaiPros* (v. 2.6) software created by Dr. Markku Pirttijärvi. The basic data processing operations made on the raw data are:

1. Prefiltering and decimation/averaging of the FG sensor data,
2. Computation of barometric height and altitude from barometric pressure and DEM,
3. Computation of rectangular X and Y map coordinates (ETRS89-TM35FIN or UTM on WGS84),
4. Computation of GNSS flight height using GNSS altitude, DEM, and a geoid model,
5. Computation of running profile distance coordinate and azimuth/heading angle,
6. Application of flux-gate sensor calibration (based on a separate calibration measurement),

7. Computation of the raw and corrected magnetic total field from XYZ components.

After basic processing, 1) barometric flight altitude is corrected for linear pressure change and verified against GNSS altitude, 2) data were visually checked and unnecessary data (e.g. flights between the home base and the survey area) are cut away, 3) base station correction is applied to daily magnetic total field data, 4) all flights are combined and clipped inside the survey area and where ever flight paths cross each other due to buildings, and finally, 5) Fourier transform based low pass (LP) filter with a cut-off wavelength of about $1/3$ of line separation is applied to corrected total field.

An important part of Radai's magnetic survey method is the use of equivalent layer modelling (ELM) to determine some corrections (tie-line corrections, heading errors, micro-levelling/decorrugation) that need to be made on raw fluxgate magnetometer data before the results can be presented as maps. ELM is a process where numerical modelling and optimisation are used to find such a susceptibility model that its synthetic response fits the measured magnetic total field. The inverted susceptibility model, which is composed of a single layer of three-dimensional magnetised cells, is then used to compute the magnetic field at a constant elevation level on an even grid. Thus, ELM removes the effects of flight altitude variations and uneven sampling of the data. The size of the model elements is equal to the line separation. Because of the rather large cell size (equal to line separation) and distance to the flight height, ELM also removes high-frequency noise and artifacts (e.g., electric power lines and noise caused by the UAV engine) provided that their wavelength is short compared to the size of the elements used in the equivalent layer model. ELM is also used to level the datasets (including tie-line correction), and to find out the heading correction, and to apply these corrections to the final corrected total field at the original data locations. The final processing of MSS data into GeoTIFF grids is made using third-party software (e.g., Golden Software Surfer or QGIS).

Data processing with *RadaiPros* and *RadaiView*, which is a lightweight version of *RadaiPros* without ELM processing, has been made as easy and fast as possible. Data pre-processing and QA/QC is made right after the flight data has been uploaded into Google Drive folder. During the survey, QA/QC confirms the data quality and makes sure all flight lines become measured as planned. At the end of the day, the client is given screenshots of a) the progress made during the day and b) a compilation of the data on all survey days. Statistical information (e.g. line-km count, mean height and its standard deviation) is computed for each flight and given as the average of all the flights. Standard deviations of the fourth difference (D4) and high pass (HP) filtered data are used as measures of data quality.

4.3 Magnetic data example

Figure 7 shows a map of total magnetic intensity (TMI) over the Lintumaansuo test area about 20 km north of Oulu, Finland. The map is computed using the equivalent layer modelling (ELM) method at a constant height of 50 m above the ground surface defined by DEM. The grid sampling is 25 m by 25 m, which is half of the line separation. The magnetic data was measured during the EM test survey in June 2024 (see Chapter 5). The survey site is characterised by two parallel SE-NW directed magnetic (and conductive) zones, which are assumed to contain pyrrhotite and/or black schists. The host rock consists of the metasediments of Kiiminki schist area.

In addition to the total intensity of the magnetic field, RAD provides several derivatives of the TMI. These include, the first and second vertical derivatives, horizontal gradient, tilt gradient and total gradient. These derivatives can be computed at any height level (downward or upward continuation) and for vertical magnetic induction to provide reduced to pole (RTP) magnetic field.

Figure 7. Example of a magnetic map based on Radai's magnetic survey system. The data are computed by ELM at a constant height of 50 m above ground.

In the AGEMERA project, the data are delivered in the format of GeoTIFF grids with embedded coordinate reference system (CRS) geographic (longitude/latitude) WGS84 coordinates (EPSG:4326). The transformation from projected coordinates (ETR89-TM35FIN or WGS84-UTMxx) where magnetic data processing is made to geographic coordinates is made using third-party software (e.g. Golden Software Surfer or QGIS).

5. Electromagnetic survey system

Figure 8 illustrates two operation modes for drone EM surveys. In the semi-airborne mode on the left, the EM transmitter (Tx) is a large loop ($\varnothing > 100$ m) laid on the ground, and the airborne 3-component EM receiver (Rx) is towed by a drone. Because of the attenuation of the EM signal, the surveying is limited to the vicinity (< 2 km) of the fixed transmitter, and therefore, this operation mode is more suited for the investigation of known targets. Moreover, accurate data interpretation requires that measurements are repeated using additional 1-3 transmitter loop locations around the target.

In the single-drone configuration on the right, a small transmitter loop ($\varnothing \approx 1$ m) is attached rigidly onto the same drone that tows the receiver unit. This fully airborne “Slingram” method avoids the need to move and lay down the ground loop, and, thus, allows more efficient mapping of larger areas. The downside is the smaller depth of investigation and the increased flight risk because a longer ($L > 50$ m) tow line is needed to obtain a greater depth of investigation.

Figure 8. The two operation modes considered in the Louhi EM survey system.

In the past, RAD has focused on developing the EM receiver unit using the fixed ground loop transmitter in the semi-airborne version of the Louhi EM system. In AGEMERA Task 3.1 RAD aims to develop the fully airborne single-drone EM system that can be used to map the conductivity, or its reciprocal the resistivity, of the ground.

5.1 Louhi EM transmitter

Figure 9 illustrates the transmitter electronics unit of the Louhi EM system. It is designed to be small and lightweight, because the same unit will be used both in the semi-airborne version and in the single-drone system. The loop size and transmitter

current can vary depending on the target under investigation and selected equipment. Now, the size of the ground transmitter loop is 100 m by 100 m and the current is 0.5-5 A depending on the frequency. In the single-drone system the diameter of the small transmitter loop is about 1 meter, and the current is 20-30 A. All three frequencies (2.3, 4.6, 9.2 kHz) are transmitted simultaneously and triggered once per second using GPS PPS signal. In Figure 9, the black cylinder on the top is the GNSS antenna, which can be connected to the receiver unit via a longer antenna cable. The Arduino Due microcontroller is on the backside of the board. The transmitter can be powered by a generator, in which case a separate DC power source is also used or directly by LiPo batteries as would be made in the single-drone system.

Figure 9. The Louhi EM transmitter electronics unit.

Figure 10 shows Pekka Korkeakangas, Radai's electrical engineer who has designed and built the Louhi EM system, setting up the ground loop transmitter. The transmitter electronics unit is inside the see-through plastic box on top of a DC power source, which is on top of a black plastic box containing the impedance tuner that is used to maximise the current in the loop used in the semi-airborne version of Louhi EM system.

Figure 11 shows the mould used to create the loop windings of the small transmitter loop. The mould is made of plywood and it allows the bending of the hollow aluminium pipe few times around in a spiral shape. The diameter of the transmitter loop varies between 0.9 and 1.1 m. In theory, each loop winding (N) increases the magnetic moment (M) of the transmitter loop by a factor of one since $M = NIA$ (I = current and A = surface area).

Figure 10. Pekka Korkeakangas is setting up the Louhi EM ground loop transmitter.

Figure 11. The mould used to create the loop windings for the small transmitter.

Figure 12 shows the small transmitter loop installed in the Coot VTOL drone. The gaps between the windings reduce self-inductance in the loop. Plastic cable ties are used to attach the loop in a rigid form so that the individual windings are not in contact with each other. Together with the transmitter electronics unit (Figure 9), the mass of the loop structure is less than one kilogram. The small transmitter draws its power from the same 2x6S LiPo batteries which Coot VTOL drone uses for flying. The transmitter is estimated to reduce the endurance by only about 10-20% during the flight.

Figure 12. The small transmitter loop installed in the Coot VTOL drone.

5.2 Louhi EM receiver

Figure 13 illustrates the 3-component Louhi EM receiver. The receiver coils are interconnected and act as a supporting part of the receiver unit that operates like a glider. Elevons (tailerons) are connected via push bars to servos that are controlled by a Pixhawk4 autopilot, which actively stabilises the flight of the glider. The receiver itself is a stand-alone device based on a 32-bit Arduino Due microcontroller. It does not measure a time series of the raw data signal, i.e., voltage induced in receiver loops. Instead, the pre-amplified and bandpass filtered data are stacked over a sampling period of 1 s. The data are stored on an SD card and read to PC laptop via USB port. The data I/O, setup of the system parameters, visualisation of raw data signals, and the final processing of the recorded data is made on a PC using dedicated software written in

Python. Based on an in-house calibration method and the IMU orientation data, the final processed data are represented as north, east and down (NED) components of magnetic flux density (B-field) in picoteslas (pT). The digital signal processing (DSP) in the post-processing phase allows manipulation of the recorded data. For example, the receiver can be re-calibrated and old survey data can be reprocessed to provide better results in case the receiver loop has changed its shape during the survey.

Figure 13. Markus Kumpula operates the 3-component Louhi EM receiver.

Technical details of the Louhi EM system are listed in Table 5. Considering that the flight speed of the Coot VTOL drone is ca. 20 m/s, the spatial sampling of the data varies between 15-30 m depending on the wind direction and intensity. The maximum duration of the survey flights is about one hour in semi-airborne surveys and (estimated) 45 minutes in single-drone surveys. Thus, the maximum flight length varies between 70 km (semi-airborne) and 50 km (single-drone).

Table 5. Technical parameters of Louhi EM system

Parameter	Value
Frequencies	2.3, 4.6, 9.2 kHz
Sampling time	1 s
IMU accuracy	0.2° (yaw) and 0.03° (pitch & roll)
Parameter (transmitter)	Value
Loop size	100 m by 100 m (ground loop) Diameter 0.9- 1.1 m (small transmitter)
Current	0.5-5 A (ground loop) 20-30 A (small transmitter)
Power source	6 S LiPo (45 V) small transmitter uses VTOL drone batteries
Parameter (receiver)	Value
Mass	1.5 kg
Power source	3S Llon
Recording time	1 s
Resolution	ca. 1 fT
Noise level	50 fT

5.3 EM data processing

The data measured with Radai's Louhi EM system are processed and interpreted using either *Aeminv* (ver 3.3) software and 1D layered earth modelling and inversion or the 3D modelling and inversion of *Lempo3D* software. The results of *Aeminv* are presented as maps of the (apparent) conductivity, or its reciprocal, the resistivity of each model layer. *Lempo3D* can be used to model the data using arbitrarily oriented dipping prisms-like bodies or a 3D mesh volume that embeds the whole volume below the survey area. In the latter case, the results of *Lempo3D* can be presented as full 3D volume meshes or as vertical or horizontal slices cut out from the 3D mesh.

Aeminv was created by Dr. Markku Pirttijärvi when he worked for the University of Oulu (Pirttijärvi et al, 2014). Since then, it has been improved by RAD. The main advantages of *Aeminv* over other layered earth inversion programs is the ability to take the magnetic susceptibility into account by using joint (combined) inversion of EM and magnetic data. *Aeminv* uses lateral (Occam-type) constraining either along the profile or between neighbouring profiles. It also supports the processing of large datasets (EMD and XYZ file formats) natively. Unfortunately, 1D layered earth model does not suit the interpretation of fixed ground loop EM data. This is because the (true) three-

dimensional conductivity structure of the earth alters the EM response so that 1D model is incapable of producing the measured data.

Lempo3D software was created by Dr. Markku Pirttijärvi especially for Louhi EM data. It uses an approximate EM modelling method based on an integral equation solution (Pirttijärvi et al, 2002). It also contains Occam-type of constraining for model smoothness. The inversion method utilises the adjoint solution of McGillivray et al. (1994) to determine the Jacobian (sensitivity matrix). However, the inversion method has not been thoroughly tested. Presently, the inversion has been tested using synthetic data only since the phase calibration of Louhi EM data is missing. Unlike *Aeminv*, *Lempo3D* software has several useful functions to redefine the measured Louhi EM response (East-North-Up components of the B-field). For example, the data can be defined as the ratio between east or north and up components (B_e/B_u or B_n/B_u). It can also be used to visualise the data as maps and profile plots, to cut the data inside the survey area, to divide the data into separate profile lines, and to save and export the EM data in the EMD file format used in Radai's EM software.

5.4 EM data examples

In the following two examples from field tests with the Louhi EM device are provided. The first one from Lintumaansuo utilises the large fixed ground loop transmitter. The second one from Toppilansaari is one of the few field tests made with the small transmitter loop so far.

5.4.1 Lintumaansuo semi-airborne survey

In June 2024, RAD made an EM survey over the Lintumaansuo test site located about 20 km north of Oulu. The survey was made using a fixed ground loop system configuration and two loop locations. Figure 13 shows the topographic map of the survey area and the flight path from one of the survey flights. The line separation is 50 m and their azimuth is their azimuth is 45 degrees from map east. The locations of the two loops are depicted on the map too.

Figure 14 shows the 10-base logarithm of the amplitude of the EM response (pT) for the East (top), North (middle) and Up components (bottom) at 2.3 kHz (left), 4.6 kHz (middle) and 9.2 kHz (right) from the flight illustrated in Figure 11 for transmitter loop #2 (green one). Phase data are not shown, because the survey was made before the phase calibration was ready.

Figure 14. Flight lines from an EM survey made over the Lintumaansuo test site. The small red and green polygons depict the two transmitter loop locations. The survey area is outlined by the red rectangle. Topographic map and digital elevation model (DEM) by National Land Survey of Finland.

At first glance the data in Figure 14 looks good. The data are continuous from one line to another, and the four, perpendicular tie-lines blend with the actual flight lines relatively well. The synthetic EM response of the loop, however, reveals that the east and north components lack the minima towards the north and east. The minima should appear because the loop does not have a primary magnetic field in azimuthal direction. Closer inspection of the mechanical structure of the receiver coil system showed that its XYZ components were interconnected and a part of their data was captured in other components. Although, the data from the Lintumaansuo test cannot be used in inversion, the maps show that the minimum and maximum values of the response are less than 50 fT and 1 nT, respectively. Moreover, the data are relatively smooth on the far edge from the transmitter, indicating that the noise level is less than 50 fT.

Figure 15. Amplitude maps from Lintumaansuo EM test survey for loop #2. Maps show the East (top), North (middle) and Up component (bottom) at 2.3 kHz (left), 4.6 kHz (middle) and 9.2 kHz (right).

A more recent field survey made after fixing the receiver loop electrical connections showed similar amplitude levels but improved amplitude pattern (minima) that complies with the numerical modelling better. Moreover, the amount of striping along the flight line direction was much less than in Figure 14. Since the survey in question was made for a client that is not an AGEMERA partner, the results are not shown here.

5.4.2 Toppilansaari walking test

The focus of Radai's development work has been on the EM receiver and it has been much easier and more beneficial to test the receiver using a fixed ground loop transmitter. Therefore, the development of the single-drone system utilizing the small transmitter loop has been slow. One field test with the small transmitter was made in December 2023 in Toppilansaari in Oulu by Pekka Korkeakangas and Timo Matalampi. In the test, the small loop was kept stationary as the receiver was carried few hundred meters away from the transmitter. Thus, the measurement mimics a

fixed loop measurement. No data (time, position, current, attitude) was measured by the transmitter unit. Moreover, a down-sized version of the receiver loop was used that was not calibrated to yield east, north, and up components.

Figure 15 shows the path from the walking survey on a Google Earth map on the left and in rectangular map coordinates (ETRS89-TM35FIN) on the right. The coloured dots in the map on the right corresponds to the amplitude of the third coil component at 9.2 kHz. The transmitter is located close to the parking lot in the SE corner of the map. The profile starts from the wave barrier (bulwark) in the NW corner and ends about 50 m away from the transmitter (the small blue symbol in SE corner of the right map in Figure 15). The response amplitude is naturally strongest near the end of the profile closest to the transmitter.

Figure 15. Walking test with fixed small transmitter loop. Left: The location of the walking path (coloured line) and transmitter (pin mark) on Google Earth map. Right: The same path in ETRS-TM35FIN coordinates showing the data as coloured dots.

To study the quality of the EM data from the walking survey, Figure 16 shows profile plots of measured raw data (component #3) using a special log₁₀-normalisation which preserves the sign of the EM data. The red (in-phase component) curve in the bottom plot (9.2 kHz) shows the same data as the map on the right in Figure 15. Although the y-axis shows picotesla as data unit, the values are arbitrary, because the receiver has not been calibrated at all.

Figure 16. Toppilansaari walking test with fixed small transmitter loop. Raw log₁₀-normalised in-phase (red) and quadrature (blue) components are shown for the component #3 at all three frequencies (2.3, 4.6, 9.2 kHz) from top to bottom.

The plots in Figure 16 show the gradual increase of response amplitude as the distance to the transmitter reduces. It also shows a distinctive bump in the middle of the profile (distance ca. 180 m) at all three frequencies. The bump coincides with the small bend appearing in the profile path (cf. Figure 15). Since the data are not rotated along geographic coordinate axes, the bump appears from the fact that the primary field changes as the receiver gets rotated horizontally with respect to the transmitter.

It is also important to note, that the first 70 m from the beginning of the profile shows noisy data. This indicates that the small transmitter is powerful enough to create primary field that exceeds the noise level (estimated to be ca. 0.1 pT for the down-sized receiver) almost 350 m away from the loop. The test, thus, verifies that the small transmitter unit is powerful enough to be used in the fully airborne single-drone version of the Louhi EM system. Almost as importantly, there is enough data resolution to capture the weak secondary EM field from the measured total field.

At the time of the walking test in December 2023, the small receiver had not been calibrated and it was incapable of providing east, north, and up data as it does now. Furthermore, the transmitter did not save the location, the attitude (roll, pitch, yaw) or current in the loop as the present version equipped with an IMU unit does. Once the phase calibration (receiver-transmitter time synchronisation) has been accomplished, several tests can be made with the next version of the small-transmitter loop setup. This means that the Lempo3D pre-processing and inversion software needs to be updated to account for the attitude (roll, pitch, yaw) of the transmitter and the variable distance and height difference between the transmitter and receiver.

6. Conclusions & road ahead

This report, designated as Deliverable 3.1 (D3.1) of the AGEMERA project, provides an overview of the status of the integrated drone-based geophysical survey system developed by RAD in task T3.1 of the AGEMERA project. It also serves as a demonstrator for the technology used in T3.1.

Three measurement systems (radiometric, magnetic and electromagnetic) have been implemented on Coot VTOL drone. The radiometric method, however, cannot be deployed at the same time as magnetic and EM because of the mass/weight of the gamma ray detector. The same Coot VTOL drone is used as the platform for all three methods.

The outcome from the tests made with the radiometric system are two-fold. On one hand the radiometric system was successfully installed on a VTOL drone and the flight tests were successful, but on the other hand, the radiometric system itself was not working as well as expected. The number of counts per second are maybe too low for practical surveying, at least in Finnish conditions, where the overburden masks the response from the bedrock.

Radai's existing magnetic surveys system has been successfully installed on a Coot drone and the data obtained from the tests was found to be of good quality. Compared to the Puffin VTOL drones that Radai has previously used for magnetic surveys, the bigger size of the Coot drone provides almost 100% increase in efficiency due to the longer flight endurance (2 h vs 1 h).

The development of a fully airborne EM system has succeeded only partially. The field tests made in August 2024 show that the semi-airborne version of the Louhi EM system is finally fully operational except for the lack of phase calibration (transmitter-receiver time synchronisation). Moreover, field tests made with the small transmitter loop on the ground level were successful as well as the flight tests with inactive transmitter loop. When active, however, the transmitter's EM field sometimes distorts the autopilot of the Coot drone, thus, preventing safe flight operations. The first field tests with the single-drone Louhi EM system are expected after successful integration tests in 2025.

In the post-Month 26 (M26) phase, task T3.1 of the AGEMERA project will focus on the field tests in Bosnia-Herzegovina and Bulgaria, the processing of the data obtained therein, the fusion and sharing of the data, and the further development of data processing software (*Lempo3D* and *Aeminv*). This phase will involve collaboration with other tasks in WP3 and, particularly, in WP4.

Strategies for further improvement of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) include successful integration of the small transmitter loop in the Coot VTOL drone and field tests made with the single-drone version of Radai's Louhi EM survey system. At the completion of the project, the TRL for the drone-based EM survey system will have

reached TRL5. It should be noted that the magnetic survey system alone has reached TRL9 already.

RAD will also continue developing the software and best practices to process and to interpret the Louhi EM data. The software development work is made mostly outside the AGEMERA project, although AGEMERA will greatly benefit from it.

In summary, significant advancements in data processing, fusion, sharing, and application development are expected during the post-M26 period of the AGEMERA project.

References

- McGillivray, P.R., Oldenburg, D.W., Ellis, R.G., and Habashy, T.M., 1994. Calculation of the sensitivities for the frequency-domain electromagnetic problem. *Geophys. J. Int.*, 116, 1-4.
- Pirttijärvi, M., Pietilä, R., Hattula, A., and Hjelt, S.-E., 2002. Modelling and inversion of electromagnetic data using an approximate plate model. *Geoph. Prospecting*, 50, 425-440.
- Pirttijärvi, M., Abdel Zaher, M., and Korja, T., 2014. Combined inversion of airborne electromagnetic and static magnetic field data. *Geophysica*, 50(2), 65-87.